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Wooden Boat Building for Modern Naval Architecture Learning

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ABSTRACT

Current naval architecture curriculum in Taiwan focuses on building theoretical knowledge and scientific research skills through teaching mechanics and mathematics in the early years. It's believed that shipbuilding involves complex systems thinking and that therefore design should be engaged after one has acquired solid theoretical knowledge. Students struggle however to establish integrated understanding about ships from diverse knowledge sources and various learning methods. Architecture education, on the other hand, starts with introducing students to design and model making at an early stage and these topics retain emphasis throughout their entire education. Inspired by the restoration of an old Chinese junk, the authors wanted to investigate the relevance of wooden boatbuilding for modern naval architecture learning. We designed a hands-on curriculum where students built a western sailboat model following standard procedures. Students learned about modern timber, basic carpentry skills and could exercise their spatial intelligence. We also involved a highly experienced local shipwright master. Students have reported to gain integrated understanding of design, construction, material, mechanics, aesthetics, societal and historical aspects of wooden boats. The class has elevated interests in shipbuilding and facilitated active discussions about using wooden boat building as an agent for modern shipbuilding knowledge construction.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills

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